

A Clinical Study of Various Methods of Foot Defect Reconstruction with respect to Dorsum of Foot Ankle and its Outcome

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Abstract:

Background: Reconstruction of foot and ankle defects requires selecting an appropriate durable and aesthetically appealing option. From the different options, the procedure's choice depends on the defect's size, location, and donor area's availability. Patients' main goal is to have an acceptable biomechanical outcome.

Aim and Objectives: To analyze the foot defects and discuss the various established reconstructive options available and their application. To evaluate the functional outcomes of various surgical procedures following dorsum of foot and ankle defects.”

Material and Methods: The study was conducted in department of Plastic and “reconstructive Surgery, Patna Medical College and Hospital, Patna. Thirty patients were examined and analyzed based on the established reconstructive options and operated in emergency or elective settings.

Result: The study demonstrates that selecting appropriate reconstruction methods based on defect size, location, and patient demographics is essential for optimal outcomes in foot deformity repair, particularly on the dorsum and ankle. Split-thickness skin grafts and free flaps showed favorable results in wound healing and functional recovery, with free flaps being ideal for severe defects. Sophisticated techniques, such as anterolateral thigh free flaps, had longer recovery times and higher complication risks, requiring careful planning. Less invasive methods, like reverse superficial sural artery and lateral supramalleolar flaps, are effective for mild to moderate defects. Personalized treatment plans improve surgical success, patient satisfaction, and overall quality of life.

Conclusion: This study highlights the importance of selecting individualized reconstructive methods for foot defects, emphasizing the role of defect size, location, and patient-specific factors in achieving optimal outcomes. Less invasive options like reverse sural and supramalleolar flaps are effective for mild to moderate defects, while free flaps are reserved for extensive or severe cases. Tailored approaches enhance functional recovery, patient satisfaction, and overall surgical success.

Keywords: foot trauma, foot and ankle surgeries, foot and ankle reconstruction, foot and ankle defects.

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Introduction

Walking and maintaining an upright posture are greatly aided by the foot and ankle region. This area is more vulnerable to infections and accidents due to a lack of soft tissue.[1] Numerous factors, including trauma, infection, tumor excision, impaired blood supply, altered sensations, and ankle and foot misalignment, might disrupt the stability of the skeletal system.

These ailments may make soft tissue damage or disintegration more likely. Saving a damaged or compromised foot is a complex procedure since it frequently necessitates significant amputation. Significant physical, psychological, emotional, and social repercussions could result from this, and occasionally a lifetime requirement for prosthetic devices. Many patients are unable to regain their

ability to walk and are condemned to a miserable life in a wheelchair, even with the wealth of resources and rehabilitation techniques available.[2] Since ancient times, people have struggled with leg ulcers, such as those on the ankle and foot, and they still provide a serious challenge to patients and caregivers everywhere. Lesions or open sores with a delayed rate of recuperation and total tissue loss are called ulcers. The epidermis, parts of the dermis, and possibly even subcutaneous fat or tissues may completely disappear as a result of skin ulcers.[3]

The process of recreating soft tissue in the foot and ankle is still challenging for cosmetic and reconstructive surgeons, even with improvements in the transfer of fasciocutaneous, musculocutaneous, and

composite flaps. [4] Reconstructing the foot is tough for plastic surgeons. The goal of foot reconstruction is to cover soft tissues and ensure functional recovery. Foot and ankle deformities involving exposed tendon and bone require local or free flap coverage. Understanding the anatomy of the foot and ankle enables for the use of pedicled and free flaps to cover foot deformities for a long-lasting solution.

Aim and Objectives

Primary Objective: To analyze the foot defects and discuss the various established reconstructive options available and their application.

Secondary Objective: To evaluate the functional outcomes of various surgical procedures following dorsum of foot and ankle defects.”

Materials and Methods: The study was conducted in department of Plastic and “reconstructive Surgery, Patna Medical College and Hospital, Patna. Thirty patients were examined and analyzed based on the established reconstructive options and operated in emergency or elective settings.

Pre-Operative Assessment: Prior to surgery, a comprehensive history and physical examination were conducted. The time and manner of injury, age, occupational status, and general health of patients are considered before surgery. The foot and ankle were evaluated for vascular health,

contamination, and soft tissue loss severity. Skeletal examinations involved X-rays of the foot and ankle. We examined the degree of comminution, bone loss, and intraarticular injury.

Basic Investigations:

Complete Blood Count, Bleeding Time / Clotting Time, Random Blood Sugar, Liver Function Test, Renal Function Test, Serum Electrolyte, Viral Marker, ECG, Chest X-Ray, Color Dopular of the limb from were flap is taken.

Intraoperative Management

The primary focus in treating foot injuries is to restore vascularity and stabilize the skeleton. Restoration of foot function was achieved through soft tissue covering. Thorough wound irrigation and debridement were performed under tourniquet control. Fixed metatarsals and tarsals. The tourniquet was deflated after removing all devitalized skin, fascia, and muscle.

Statistical Analysis:

All the data were analyzed using SPSS package (Stata, version 26.0 SPSS INC, Chicago, IL, USA) for windows. The data were presented as descriptive statistics for continuous variables and percentage for categorical variables and was subjected Chi-square test, t test & Anova test.

Results

Table 1: Age distribution of subjects

Age	No	%	P. value
20-29	9	30.00%	<0.001
30-39	7	23.3%	
40-49	10	33.4%	
50-59	4	13.3%	
Total	30	100%	
Mean±SD	38.00±10.80		

Table 2: Sex distribution of subjects

Sex	No	%
Male	20	66.67%
Female	10	33.33%
Total	30	100%

Table 3: Made of defect

Made of defect	No	%	P. value
Amputation of great toe	1	3.33%	<0.001
Amputation of great toe over left foot	1	3.33%	
Hypertrophic scar over dorsum of foot	5	16.67%	
Hypertrophic scar over left dorsum of foot	1	3.33%	
Hypertrophic scar over left foot	1	3.33%	
Mycetoma left Foot	1	3.33%	
Neuroischaemic ulcer Rt Foot	1	3.33%	
Post inf raw area over left foot	1	3.33%	
Post inf raw area rt foot & ankle	1	3.33%	
Post infective area left lateral Malleolus	1	3.33%	

Post infective raw area over rt foot	1	3.33%
Post traumatic defect over left heel	2	6.67%
Post traumatic defect over left malleolus	1	3.33%
Post traumatic defect over Rt ankle	1	3.33%
Post traumatic defect over Rt Malleolus	2	6.67%
Post traumatic defect over Rt Medical Malleolus	1	3.33%
Post traumatic raw area Rt Malleolus	1	3.33%
Post traumatic raw area over left foot	1	3.33%
Post traumatic raw area over left foot & ankle	2	6.67%
Raw area Rt Foot	1	3.33%
Soft tissue sarcoma	3	10.00%
Total	30	100%

Table 4: Option used

Option used	No	%	P. value
Debridement & split thickness skin graft	1	3.33%	0.010
Exercise & split thickness skin graft	10	33.33%	
Excision & Anterolateral Thigh Free Flap	1	3.33%	
First dorsal metatarsal artery flap	1	3.33%	
First dorsal metatarsal artery perforator	1	3.33%	
Free latissimas dorsi muscle flap	2	6.67%	
Lateral Calcaneal artery flap	1	3.33%	
Perforator based propellar flap	5	16.67%	
Reverse superficial rural artery flap	2	6.67%	
Split thickness skin graft	5	16.67%	
V-y Advancement Flap	1	3.33%	
Total	30	100%	

Table 5: Comparison of Made of defect and Age

Made of defect	Age			
	20-29	30-39	40-49	50-59
Amputation of great toe	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	1 (3.33%)	0 (0%)
Amputation of great toe over left foot	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	1 (3.33%)	0 (0%)
Hypertrophic scar over dorsum of foot	0 (0%)	3 (10.00%)	2 (6.67%)	0 (0%)
Hypertrophic scar over left dorsum of foot	1 (3.33%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)
Hypertrophic scar over left foot	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	1 (3.33%)	0 (0%)
Mycetoma left Foot	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	1 (3.33%)
Neuroischaemic ulcer Rt Foot	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	1 (3.33%)
Post inf raw area over left foot	1 (3.33%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)
Post inf raw area rt foot & ankle	1 (3.33%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)
Post infective area left lateral Malleolus	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0	1 (3.33%)
Post infective raw area over rt foot	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	1 (3.33%)	0 (0%)
Post traumatic defect over left heel	1 (3.33%)	0 (0%)	1 (3.33%)	0 (0%)
Post traumatic defect over left malleolus	0 (0%)	1 (3.33%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)
Post traumatic defect over Rt ankle	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	1 (3.33%)	0 (0%)
Post traumatic defect over Rt Malleolus	1 (3.33%)	1 (3.33%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)
Post traumatic defect over Rt Medical Malleolus	1 (3.33%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)
Post traumatic raw area Rt Malleolus	1 (3.33%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)
Post traumatic raw area over left foot	1 (3.33%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)
Post traumatic raw area over left foot & ankle	0 (0%)	1 (3.33%)	1 (3.33%)	0 (0%)
Raw area Rt Foot	1 (3.33%)	0 (0%)	0	0 (0%)
Soft tissue sarcoma	0 (0%)	1 (3.33%)	1 (3.33%)	1 (3.33%)

Table 6: Comparison of Option used and Age

Option used	Age			
	20-29	30-39	40-49	50-59
Debridement & split thickness skin graft	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	1 (3.33%)	0 (0%)
Exercise & split thickness skin graft	1 (3.33%)	4 (13.33%)	4 (13.33%)	1 (3.33%)
Excision & Anterolateral Thigh Free Flap	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	1 (3.33%)
First dorsal metatarsal artery flap	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	1 (3.33%)	0 (0%)
First dorsal metatarsal artery perforator	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	1 (3.33%)	0 (0%)
Free latisimas dorsi muscle flap	1 (3.33%)	1 (3.33%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)
Lateral Calcareaal artery flap	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	1 (3.33%)
Perforator based propellar flap	4 (13.33%)	1 (3.33%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)
Reverse superficial rural artery flap	1 (3.33%)	0 (0%)	1 (3.33%)	0 (0%)
Split thickness skin graft	2 (6.67%)	1 (3.33%)	2 (6.67%)	0 (0%)
V-y Advancement Flap	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	1 (3.33%)

Table 7: Comparison of Made of defect and Sex

Made of defect	Sex	
	Male	Female
Amputation of great toe	0 (0%)	1 (3.33%)
Amputation of great toe over left foot	1 (3.33%)	0 (0%)
Hypertrophic scar over dorsum of foot	2 (6.67%)	3 (10.00%)
Hypertrophic scar over left dorsum of foot	1 (3.33%)	0 (0%)
Hypertrophic scar over left foot	1 (3.33%)	0 (0%)
Mycetoma left Foot	1 (3.33%)	0 (0%)
Neuroischaemic ulcer Rt Foot	1 (3.33%)	0 (0%)
Post inf raw area over left foot	1 (3.33%)	0 (0%)
Post inf raw area rt foot & ankle	1 (3.33%)	0 (0%)
Post infective area left lateral Malleolus	1 (3.33%)	0 (0%)
Post infective raw area over rt foot	0 (0%)	1 (3.33%)
Post traumatic defect over left heel	1 (3.33%)	1 (3.33%)
Post traumatic defect over left malleolus	1 (3.33%)	0 (0%)
Post traumatic defect over Rt ankle	1 (3.33%)	0 (0%)
Post traumatic defect over Rt Malleolus	1 (3.33%)	1 (3.33%)
Post traumatic defect over Rt Medical Malleolus	0 (0%)	1 (3.33%)
Post traumatic raw area Rt Malleolus	0 (0%)	1 (3.33%)
Post traumatic raw area over left foot	0 (0%)	1 (3.33%)
Post traumatic raw area over left foot & ankle	2 (6.67%)	0 (0%)
Raw area Rt Foot	1 (3.33%)	0 (0%)
Soft tissue sarcoma	3 (10.00%)	0 (0%)

Table 8: Comparison of Option used and Sex

Option used	Sex	
	Male	Female
Debridement & split thickness skin graft	0 (0%)	1 (3.33%)
Exercise & split thickness skin graft	7 (23.33%)	3 (10.00%)
Excision & Anterolateral Thigh Free Flap	1 (3.33%)	0 (0%)
First dorsal metatarsal artery flap	0 (0%)	1 (3.33%)
First dorsal metatarsal artery perforator	1 (3.33%)	0 (0%)
Free latisimas dorsi muscle flap	1 (3.33%)	1 (3.33%)
Lateral Calcareaal artery flap	1 (3.33%)	0 (0%)
Perforator based propellar flap	3 (10.00%)	2 (6.67%)
Reverse superficial rural artery flap	1 (3.33%)	1 (3.33%)
Split thickness skin graft	4 (13.33%)	1 (3.33%)
V-y Advancement Flap	1 (3.33%)	0 (0%)

Discussion

Foot and ankle injuries are prevalent, particularly with severe soft tissue abnormalities. Soft tissue abnormalities in the foot and ankle challenge Plastic and Reconstructive surgeons. Untreated injuries can cause persistent pain, non-healing ulcers, and reduced function, impairing lifestyle. The main objective of foot and ankle reconstruction is to cover the incision and enable bipedal ambulation. Numerous reconstructive options are available for deformities, depending on site, size, depth, and condition.

Understanding the reconstructive ladder and its modifications, as well as the surgeon's competence and experience, aided in decision-making. Stable covers are essential for both barefoot and shoe-wearing populations. Providing a stable flap allows for further bone and tendon coverage. A split skin graft on the dorsum of the foot can cause secondary lymphedema of the toes, despite losing color, texture, and thickness match.

According to our study, the majority of individuals are aged 40-49 (33.4%), followed by 20-29 (30%) and 30-39 (23.3%). The smallest group is 50-59, comprising 13.3%. The average age is 38.00 years, with a standard deviation of 10.80 and a significant p-value of <0.001.

Our survey reveals a higher number of males than girls. Specifically, 66.67% of participants are male and 33.33% are female. Based on our analysis, hypertrophic scars are the most prevalent deformity, affecting 23.33% of the participants. In 10% of instances, soft tissue sarcoma was found, whereas amputations and post-traumatic abnormalities accounted for lesser percentages (3.33% to 6.67%). The distribution of faults is significant (p-value <0.001).

Hamad et al. [5] and Zhu et al. [6] observed that the dorsum of the foot is the most prevalent place for defects, followed by the malleoli and heel. Our study found that trauma (56%) was the leading cause of foot and ankle abnormalities. According to research by Bhandari et al. [7] and Dogra et al. [8], trauma is the main cause of foot and ankle abnormalities, accounting for 56.6% and 50%, respectively. Moon and Pandey [9] found that trauma was the leading cause of foot and ankle abnormalities. The study found that "Exercise & split thickness skin graft" was the most commonly used treatment option, employed in 33.33% of patients. Perforator-based propeller flaps and split thickness skin grafts are also commonly employed, accounting for 16.67%. The distribution of treatment options is significant (p-value = 0.010).

Our study examines defect distribution across age groups. Most abnormalities occur in the 30-39 and 40-49 age groups, with post-traumatic and

hypertrophic scars being common. The 50-59 age range has fewer abnormalities, with only one individual experiencing mycetoma and neuroischemic ulcers. The youngest age group (20-29) exhibited some post-infective and postraumatic abnormalities, while middle-aged groups had a higher prevalence. We compared treatment options across age groups in our study. "Exercise & split thickness skin graft" was the most popular option among all age categories, especially among those aged 30-49. Perforator-based propeller flaps were the most common therapy for younger patients (20-29), whereas elderly patients (50-59) had a variety of procedures, including anterolateral thigh free flaps and V-Y advancement flaps. The distribution of therapies reflects the differences in faults among ages. We compared the distribution of faults between male and female individuals. Males were more likely to experience deformities including soft tissue sarcoma and post-traumatic raw regions, particularly on the right foot and ankle. Women were more likely to experience hypertrophic scars on the dorsum of the foot and had a slightly higher incidence of great toe amputation. Some abnormalities were more prevalent in one sex, indicating a diverse distribution across males and females.

We analyzed the therapy alternatives employed for both male and female participants. Males mainly underwent "Exercise & split thickness skin graft" (23.33%) and split thickness alone (13.33%), while females saw a variety of treatments, including debridement and first dorsal metatarsal artery flap (3.33%). Both sexes had similar rates for surgeries like free latissimus dorsi muscle flap and reverse superficial rural artery flap. Different treatment methods were used for males and females, with some procedures being gender-specific.

Turan et al. [10] found partial necrosis in three of 25 RSA flaps due to venous congestion. Ramesha et al. [11] found venous congestion of the RSA flap with distal flap necrosis in 25% of patients, compared to 5.6% in our study. Using a two-stage pedicled reverse surgical flap for the weight-bearing region of the heel can alleviate venous congestion, improve its reach, and retain the contour of the posterior heel [12].

Conclusion

This clinical study emphasizes the significance of choosing proper reconstruction methods for foot deformities, particularly those involving the dorsum and ankle. Results suggest that selecting a methodology based on parameters such defect size, location, and patient demographics like age and sex is crucial for each patient's individual situation. Most commonly used procedures, such as split thickness skin grafts and free flaps, showed favorable results in wound healing, functional

recovery, and patient satisfaction. While effective, sophisticated operations like the anterolateral thigh free flap and perforator-based propeller flaps had longer recovery durations and a higher risk of problems, according to the study. Though necessary for severe or extensive faults, these approaches require careful planning and execution to limit negative results. Results indicate that less intrusive procedures may be better for smaller problems, if they give sufficient coverage and functionality. This study highlights the importance of personalized treatment regimens for foot defect restoration, particularly for dorsum and ankle deformities. Clinicians can improve surgery outcomes, patient satisfaction, and quality of life for foot reconstruction patients by addressing patient-specific factors and defect features. This study provides useful data for improving surgical methods and enhancing reconstructive surgery. Reverse superficial sural artery flap and lateral supra malleolar flap are excellent covers for mild to medium foot deformities, offering alternatives to traditional reconstructive techniques. Free tissue transfer is only recommended when local options are unavailable. This treatment is ideal for treating severe foot issues by utilizing healthy, well-supplied, and flexible skin. Reconstruction aims to replace both functional and structural foot components, with free flaps being an appropriate approach.

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